

Biographies of Eminent Monks

also known as “高僧傳”, “Memoirs of Eminent Monks”, “Gaoseng Zhuan”

By Edward A S Ross, University of Reading

Entry tags: Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Mahayana Buddhism, Religious Group, Chinese Buddhism, Text, Buddhist Traditions, Indian Buddhist Traditions, Monasticism, Chinese Buddhist text, Religious History, Scholastic Buddhism

The 'Biographies of Eminent Monks' (高僧傳; 'Gaoseng Zhuan') is a compilation of the lives of over 500 Buddhist figures from 67 CE to 519 CE. This 14-chapter volume became the widely accepted basis for Chinese Buddhist, historical biography literature from the 6th century CE onwards. Extending from China's first interactions with Buddhism to the Liang Dynasty, the text of 'The Biographies of Eminent Monks' discusses Buddhist figures that were well known during the time of Shi Huijiao (慧皎) (497-554 CE), the compiler and author. Huijiao was originally from the district of Shangyu in Kuaiji, an administrative region located to the south of Hangzhou Bay. He trained to be a scholar monk and practiced at Jiexiang Temple on Kuaiji Mountain (now Xianglu Mountain), where he eventually began work on his 'Biographies of Eminent Monks'. According to Shi Daoxuan's (道宣) 'Supplement to the Biographies of Eminent Monks' (續高僧傳; 'Xu Gaoseng Zhuan'), Huijiao preached consistently during the spring and summer and wrote commentaries during the fall and winter. He only worked on historical research and compilation for the biographies in his spare time between reading religious texts and attending lectures. In his postface to the 'Biographies of Eminent Monks', Huijiao describes the wide breadth of sources he used to compile this text. He compares the different compilations of biographies prior to his own work, criticizing their "lack of proof" and the fact that they "leave a great deal of information absent." Huijiao explains that he used oral testimony from elders and historical and geographical works from most of the historical dynasties mentioned throughout the 'Biographies of Eminent Monks' to supplement the previously-written hagiographies of Buddhist figures. Although he never directly compares himself to a historian in his postface, scholars have generally determined that, based on his methods and tone, Huijiao did believe he was a Buddhist historian improving on previous hagiographical works. This compilation was meant to act as an example for how Buddhist biographies were meant to be written in Huijiao's eyes. He removes the "undeserved compliments and repetition" while focusing on the "abandonment of glory and affection" in the lives of eminent figures. The text itself, consisting of 14 chapters, has 13 chapters of biographies and a final chapter with Huijiao's postface. The biographies are divided into 10 categories: scriptural translation (1), doctrinal exegesis (2), supernatural powers (3), meditative practice (4), Vinaya exhortation (5), self-immolation (6), scriptural recitation (7), benevolent cause (8), scriptural intoners (9), and recitation guides (10). Each section ends with a short commentary by Huijiao that ties together the themes of the biographies. This new structure, combined with Huijiao's gathered prose, made it one of the most popular sources of Buddhist hagiography in China, surpassing all previous biographical compilations. In fact, this structure was used as the basis for later compilations of Chinese Buddhist biographies. Daoxuan's 'Supplement to the Biographies of Eminent Monks' and Zanning's (贊寧) 'Biographies of Eminent Monks in the Song Dynasty' (宋高僧傳; 'Song Gaoseng Zhuan') were two of the most influential later texts.

Date Range: 67 CE - 519 CE

Region: Liang Dynasty

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China, China, East Asia

This is the estimated region of the Liang Dynasty, where the author Shi Huijiao originated and composed the text, in the early sixth century CE. The early readership for this text likely started in this region but expanded to the Greater China area as regimes changed.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

—Source 1: Shinohara, Koichi. "Biographies of Eminent Monks in a Comparative Perspective: The Function of the Holy in Medieval Chinese Buddhism." In 中華佛學學報第七期, Vol. 7 (1994): 477-500.

—Source 1: [Edited Chinese Text] Shi Huijiao. *Biography of Eminent Monks*. Xian: Shanxi People's Publishing House, 2013.

—Source 1: Buswell Jr., Robert and Donald Lopez Jr.. "Gaoseng zhuan." In *The Princeton Dictionary of Buddhism*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2014. 314.

—Source 1: Wright, Arthur F. "Biography and Hagiography Hui-chiao's Lives of Eminent Monks." In *Silver Jubilee Volume of the Zinbun-Kagaku-Kenkyusyo*. Kyoto: Kyoto University Press, 1954. 338-432.

—Source 1: Kieschnick, John. *The Eminent Monk: Buddhist Ideals in Medieval Chinese Hagiography*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1997.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

—Source 1 URL:

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82%B3

—Source 1 Description: [English Translation] Shi Huijiao. *The Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Tianshu Yang, translator. Edward A. S. Ross, editor. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

—Source 1 URL: <http://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/id/eprint/364>

—Source 1 Description: Wang, Mei-Hsiu. "Cultural identities as reflected in the literature of the Northern and Southern dynasties period (4th-6th centuries A.D)." PhD thesis, University of Leeds, 2007.

—Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685322-10612P04>

—Source 1 Description: Lee, Sangyop. "'The Invention of the 'Eminent Monk': Understanding the Biographical Craft of the Gaoseng zhuan through the Mingseng zhuan." *T'oung Pao* Vol. 106, No. 1-2 (2020): 87-170.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

—Source 1 URL: <http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/T50n2059>

—Source 1 Description: [Original Chinese Text] CBETA 電子佛典集成; 大正藏 (T); 第 50 冊; No.2059

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

— Incised or Inscribed

Notes: Several versions are found in the various Chinese Buddhist Canons. Woodblock cuts are preserved in the Tripitaka Koreana and Qianlong Tripitaka.

Method of inscription

— Knife

— Stamped

Notes: There are at least 22 extant versions of the text preserved in various Chinese Buddhist Canons. The standard version comes from the Taishō Shinshū Daizōkyō. The first printed edition is in the Kaibao Canon from the Song Dynasty.

Color or black

— Black

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

— Paper

- ↳ Specify type of paper
 - Specify: 14 fascicles

– Wood

- ↳ Species
 - Specify: Various, depending on collection

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: Certain woodblock collections and preserved printed versions are maintained in Buddhist temples in Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan. There are also several digital archive projects preserving versions of the text, including the Chinese Buddhist Electronic Text Association (CBETA) and the SAT Daizōkyō Text Database.

- ↳ Tomb
 - I don't know

- ↳ Cemetery
 - I don't know

- ↳ Temple
 - Yes

Notes: Certain woodblock collections and preserved printed versions are maintained in Buddhist temples in Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan.

- ↳ Shrine
 - I don't know

- ↳ Altar
 - I don't know

- ↳ Devotional marker
 - I don't know

- ↳ Cenotaph
 - I don't know

- ↳ Church
 - I don't know

↳ Mosque
– I don't know

↳ Synagogue
– I don't know

↳ Triumphal Arch
– I don't know

↳ Monument
– I don't know

↳ Mass Gathering Point
– I don't know

↳ Cave(s)
– I don't know

↳ Hilltops
– I don't know

↳ Other natural sanctuaries
– I don't know

↳ Boundary markers or lines
– I don't know

↳ Domestic contexts
– I don't know

↳ Library/archive
– Yes

Notes: There are several digital archive projects preserving versions of the text, including the Chinese Buddhist Electronic Text Association (CBETA) and the SAT Daizōkyō Text Database.

↳ Specify
– Specify: Certain woodblock collections and preserved printed versions are maintained in Buddhist temples in Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan. There are also several digital archive projects preserving versions of the text, including the Chinese Buddhist Electronic Text Association (CBETA) and the SAT Daizōkyō Text Database.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

Notes: The temples and archives tend to also house images and iconography, but these are not specifically associated with the text.

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– Religious space with no access (i.e. buried in foundation)

- Religious space with restricted access
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces
- All public spaces

Notes: The temples and archives tend to also house images and iconography, but these are not specifically associated with the text.

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

- No

Notes: The temples and archives tend to also house images and iconography, but these are not specifically associated with the text.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

- Yes

Notes: The temples and archives tend to also house images and iconography, but these are not specifically associated with the text.

↳ Alpha-numeric symbolism?

- I don't know

↳ Use of geometric/abstract designs?

- Yes

↳ Floral or other natural imagery?

- Yes

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

- Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

- Field doesn't know

Notes: Little is known about the specifics of HuiJiao's life, but his biography notes that he only worked on historical research and compilation for the biographies in his spare time between reading religious texts and attending lectures.

Reference: Shi Daoxuan. Supplement to the Biographies of Eminent Monks. Taishō Shinshū Daizōkyō. Taipei: Chinese Buddhist Electronic Text Association, 1988.
<http://tripitaka.cbeta.org/T50n2060T50n2060>.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

- Yes

Notes: The first printed edition of the text, found in the Kaibao Canon, was funded by Emperor Taizu of the Song Dynasty.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

- No

- ↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?
– Yes
- ↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?
– Yes
Notes: Buddhist monastics did serve as advisors in the political system. However, not all monastics served as advisors at Huijiao's time, and not all political officials were Buddhist.
- ↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?
– No
- ↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?
– No
- ↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...
– I don't know
- ↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?
– Yes
Notes: Members of the Buddhist tradition copied and preserved the text in the Chinese Buddhist Canon.
- ↳ Present full-time?
– I don't know
Notes: It is unclear if the maintenance of this texts was a dedicated full-time or part-time position, but the canon itself was monitored and copied by religious specialists.
- ↳ Present part-time?
– I don't know
Notes: It is unclear if the maintenance of this texts was a dedicated full-time or part-time position, but the canon itself was monitored and copied by religious specialists.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?
– I don't know
Notes: It is unclear if the maintenance of this texts was a dedicated position, but the canon itself was monitored and copied by religious specialists of both genders.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
– No
Notes: There are religious specialists with a variety of ethnic origins mentioned in the text itself, but there are no dedicated rules regarding those who maintain the canon.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?
– No
Notes: There are religious specialists with a variety of class origins mentioned in the text itself, but there are no dedicated rules regarding those who maintain the canon.
- ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– Yes

Notes: There are instances of religious specialists dedicating their lives to specific locations, but there are also just as many instances of religious specialists not staying in any place for long.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Religious specialists are usually provided living spaces in temples.

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Living and training spaces are usually provided within the same spaces.

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: This text is a part of the Chinese Buddhist Canon, and it is usually codified as a "History."

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: This text was researched and written by HuiJiao, a monk from the Liang Dynasty.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Notes: The Buddhist Canon continues to grow as more texts and commentaries are revealed/created. There is some debate about authenticity between groups.

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: There were significant groups of religious specialists dedicated to the oral recitation of all groups of Buddhist scripture, but these groups reduced in number significantly as more texts were written down.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

Notes: There were significant groups of religious specialists dedicated to the oral recitation of all groups of Buddhist scripture, but these groups reduced in number significantly as more text were written down.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

Notes: There is a significant belief in the Buddhist tradition that the scripture is not restricted to any language, which is why there are so many canons in so many languages and dialects.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: There is a significant belief in the Buddhist tradition that the scripture is not restricted to any language, which is why there are so many canons in so many languages and dialects.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: The intention behind the text was to preserve the biographies of these Buddhist figures for future generations, and could vary greatly. There was no specific number indicated in the text itself.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Although there are cases of Buddhists promoting the Dharma for the purpose of recruitment, there is a specific aversion to the idea of proselytism.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: There are a wide variety of differing sects that aim to reform the Buddhist tradition to a "more correct interpretation."

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: This text is considered a "History" in the Chinese Buddhist Canon.

Is there material significance to the text?

– I don't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are at least 22 extant versions of the text in Chinese Buddhist Canon collections.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: They are all considered proper, but the standard version comes from the Taishō Shinshū Daizōkyō.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: The oldest extant version of the text comes from the Kaibao Canon, which was printed in the Song Dynasty (c. 971 CE). There are at least 21 other extant versions of the text.

↳ Content of text?

– No

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: There are debates regarding which Buddhist canon is proper, but there does not appear to be any discourse related to this text.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: It is included in the Chinese Buddhist Canon.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Notes: It is included in the Chinese Buddhist Canon.

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: It discusses the lives of major Buddhist figures in Chinese history.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: The Buddhist Canon continues to grow as more texts and commentaries are revealed/created. There is some debate about authenticity between groups.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

Notes: Although there are debates about the place of some texts in the Buddhist canon, this text has not been debated.

– No

Notes: The text does allude to a variety of historical and monastic codes in the Chinese Buddhist Canon.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: The text sometimes discusses the spiritual powers of highly-realized Buddhist figures, and these are sometimes associated with the spirit.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

Notes: The spirit and body are considered to be interlinked according to the concept of dependent co-arising.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: The spirit and body are considered to be interlinked according to the concept of dependent co-arising.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

Notes: They are presented as explanations for existence.

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

–Specify: They explain existence.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: There are quite a few debates about the nature of mind and consciousness in the biographies, but the specifics of the debates are not presented in detail. See the stories in the Doctrinal Exegesis section.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E)

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: There are quite a few debates about the nature of mind and consciousness in the biographies, but the specifics of the debates are not presented in detail. See the stories in the Doctrinal Exegesis section.

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↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: There are instances in the text of highly-realized practitioners sending their spirits into other realms to practice. See the story of Shi Baozhi of the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022. https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

Notes: There are many treatise discussing this topic in Buddhism, but they do not appear in this text.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: There are many differing opinions regarding this topic, but they do not appear in detail in this text.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhists generally believe in 6 realms of rebirth: the human realm, the animal realm, the god realms, the demi-god realms, the hell realms, and the hungry ghost realms. The location of rebirth is determined by karmic levels.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The human and animal realms are in this world. The god realms and demi-god realms are considered to be above or in a cardinal direction outside of this realm, while the hell realms and hungry ghost realms are considered to be below this realm.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: The god realms and demi-god realms are considered to be above or in a cardinal direction outside of this realm, while the hell realms and hungry ghost realms are considered to be below this realm.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Notes: The god realms and demi-god realms are considered to be above or in a cardinal direction outside of this realm.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Notes: The hell realms and hungry ghost realms are considered to be below this realm.

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

Notes: There are also Buddhist beliefs in purelands, which exist past the cardinal directions or in undetermined other realms.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: All of the afterlives are subject to a time frame, and beings in those lives will die and be reborn in another afterlife once their time comes.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: There are many treatise discussing this topic in Buddhism, but they do not appear in this text.

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: There are many treatise discussing this topic in Buddhism, but they do not appear in this text.

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: There are many treatise discussing this topic in Buddhism, but they do not appear in this text.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions a variety of instances of rebirth in the human realm and animal realms. There are also plenty of torturous rebirths, like as ghosts and demons, which appear in this world.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82%F

↳ In human form?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions a variety of instances of rebirth in the human realm and animal realms.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82%F

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions a variety of instances of rebirth in the human realm and animal realms.

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https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82%F

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions a variety of instances of rebirth in the human realm and animal realms. There are also plenty of torturous rebirths, like as ghosts and demons, which appear in this world.

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↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions a variety of instances of rebirth in the human realm and animal realms. There are also plenty of torturous rebirths, like as ghosts and demons, which appear in this world.

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↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– Yes

Notes: There are several examples of debates about the nature of reincarnation and rebirth in Buddhism. There are some minor discussions in the Doctrinal Exegesis section.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022. https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions?

– Specify: There are several varying debates about the nature of reincarnation and rebirth in Buddhism.

Notes: There are some minor discussions in the Doctrinal Exegesis section.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022. https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

– Specify: There are several varying debates about the nature of reincarnation and rebirth in Buddhism.

Notes: There are some minor discussions in the Doctrinal Exegesis section.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022. https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are some discussions of how certain Buddhist figures are buried in the text. Usually, the bodies of highly-realized masters are given special treatment.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– Yes

Notes: Parts of cremation remains would be interred as relics.

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– Yes

Notes: Bones and certain purified virtues found in cremation remains were considered relics.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– Yes

Notes: There are some instances of bodies being washed and prepared in a coffin before an intended cremation. See the story of Shi Xuangao of Pingcheng.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E)

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– Yes

Notes: Formal tombs and stupas were built as a way to remember the deceased, highly-realized practitioner in quite a few stories. There are also instances of memorial plates and stelae. See the story of Zhi Dun of Mount Wozhou in Shan County.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Notes: There are quite a few instances of burials in cemeteries in the text. It also mentions different burial grounds according to spiritual attainments. See the story of Shi Zhiyan of Zhiyuan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

Notes: Although not blood related, there are instances of collected monastic tombs in the text, dedicated to the Sangha. See the story of Shi Sengyuan of Upper Dinglin Temple.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E)

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: Several of the Buddhist figures mentioned in the text were buried formally in temples or under stupas. See the story of Shi Dao'an of Wuji Temple in Changkong.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Stupa interment

Notes: See the story of Shi Xianhu of Yanxing Temple in Guanghan.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are instances of people writing memorial plates and erecting stele at tombs to honour those who died. There are also frequent visits to tombs and graves to respect or learn from the dead.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Notes: There are instances of people writing memorial plates and erecting stele at tombs to honour those who died. There are also frequent visits to tombs and graves to respect or learn from the dead.

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Notes: There are several instances of visiting the graves of deceased masters to venerate them and ponder their attainments in the text. See the story of Zhi Dun of Mount Wozhou in Shan County.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross.

Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong

Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– Yes

Notes: There are several instances in the text of people visiting stupas and burial sites to venerate masters and the Buddha. See the story of Shi Baoyun of Mount Liuhe.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: A variety of deities and spirits appear throughout the text as supporting characters.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts are seen by living beings in the text, both in dreams and when awake. See the story of Shi Huiwei of Chang'an.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits are able to physically affect living beings. See the story of Shi Huijing of Yunfeng Temple in the Southern Sea.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts have knowledge of their past life and the current state of the world. See the story of Shi Huiguo of Waguan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: The ghosts and spirits have knowledge of their past life and their current predicament. See the story of Shi Huiguo of Waguan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83)

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: The ghosts and spirits have knowledge of their past life and their current predicament. See the story of Shi Huiguo of Waguan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83)

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits are able to detect the nature of living beings and affect their minds. See the story of Shi Huiguo of Waguan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83)

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits are able to detect the nature of living beings. See the story of Shi Huiguo of Waguan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83)

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Specify: They know the outcome of rebirth for certain karmic actions.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

Notes: There are some instances of supernatural beings appearing and revealing the location of worldly wealth to living beings. See the story of Shi Huiguo of Waguan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits can affect the dreams of living beings and physically beset them. See the story of Shi Huijing of Yunfeng Temple in the Southern Sea.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits can indirectly cause disaster just by being present. See the story of Dharmakṣema in Hexi Area.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits know what caused them to be reborn as ghosts. See the story of Shi Hongming of Bailin Temple in Yongxing.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits are happy when living beings perform actions that allow them to exit their current rebirth. See the story of Shi Huiguo of Waguan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits are able to bemoan their predicament and reasons for their rebirth in this fate. See the story of Shi Hongming of Bailin Temple in Yongxing.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits communicate with living beings in order to enact vengeance or request help to resolve their suffering. See the story of Shi Huiguo of Waguan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits appear as ghosts and also as living beings. See the story of Zhu Fachong of Mount Gexian in Shan County.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits can both affect the imagery in dreams and speak with a living being directly. See the story of Shi Huiguo of Waguan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

–Specify: None are clearly specified.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: There are several different types of non-human spirits across the biographies.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: There are a variety of animal and mountain spirits mentioned in the text, and they are visible and able to interact with living beings. See the story of Zhu Fo Tucheng of Zhong Temple in Yecheng.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022. [https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E)

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Notes: There are no instances in the text that mention touch or physical reactions to the spirits.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The described knowledge of non-human spirits is limited in the texts. They are able to speak to and interact with living beings in specific regions within which they are associated.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: There are some instances of non-human spirits interacting with Buddhist figures and giving them gifts for the purpose of aiding Buddhist practice in the text. See the story of Shi Daoliang of Duobao Temple to the North of the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated

by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Notes: There are some instances of non-human spirits interacting with Buddhist figures and giving them gifts for the purpose of aiding Buddhist practice in the text. See the story of Shi Daoliang of Duobao Temple to the North of the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Notes: There are is one example of a spirit causing trouble before it is captured by a Buddhist figure. See the story of Shi Hongming of Bailin Temple in Yongxing. Most of the spirits, however, simply act as ill omens.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are a few examples in the text where non-human sprits communicate with living beings. They are able to speak to and interact with living beings in specific regions within which they are associated. Most, however, are simply seen.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: There are a few examples in the text where non-human sprits communicate with living beings. They are able to speak to and interact with living beings in specific regions within which they are associated. Most, however, are simply seen. See the story of Zhu Tanyou of Mount Chicheng in Shifeng.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Destruction of physical space

Notes: See the story of Zhu Fo Tucheng of Zhong Temple in Yecheng.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: There are a few examples of non-human spirits acting as ill omens which lead to disasters in the text. See the story of Zhu Fo Tucheng of Zhong Temple in Yecheng.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: There some examples of non-human spirits being kind and happy when meeting Buddhist figures in the text. See the story of Zhu Tanyou of Mount Chicheng in Shifeng.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: There are a few examples of non-human spirits pleading and being upset. See the story of Shi Hongming of Bailin Temple in Yongxing.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: If hungry ghosts are considered non-human. There are some allusions to their state in the text, but there are no explicit references to it in the text.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: They are able to manipulate and produce objects, such as medicine.

Notes: See the story of Shi Daoliang of Duobao Temple to the North of the Capital.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: There are several deities and heavens mentioned in the text. There are some organizations of deities presented by name, but the details of these pantheons are not discussed in this text. There are several other cosmological texts that discuss the nature and structures of Buddhist heavens, hells, and purelands.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Notes: There are several tiers of heavens and hells in Buddhist cosmology, but they are not discussed in this text.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: Tiered heavens and hells with a variety of different strata and relationships.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are many highly-attained bodhisattvas present in the text. They are beings that are present both in this world and in purelands. They are able to interact and emanate themselves into the human realm in order to help sentient beings.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

Notes: There are many highly-attained bodhisattvas present in the text. They are beings that are present both in this world and in purelands. They are able to interact and emanate themselves into the human realm in order to help sentient beings.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

Notes: There are many highly-attained bodhisattvas present in the text. They are beings that are present both in this world and in purelands. They are able to interact and emanate themselves into the human realm in order to help sentient beings.

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

Notes: There are many highly-attained bodhisattvas present in the text. They are beings that are present both in this world and in purelands. They are able to interact and emanate themselves into the human realm in order to help sentient beings.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E)

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: There are some examples of bodhisattvas emanating their forms in the waking world in the text. See the story of Shi Baozhi of the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Notes: There are some examples of bodhisattvas appearing in dreams in the text. See the story of Shi Huiqian of Jiaxiang Temple in Shanyin.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Through meditative states

Notes: See the story of Shi Zhiyan of Zhiyuan Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: There are several examples of divination practices taking place in the text, but there are no instructions for how they are performed.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: Rather than a being watching over, actions produce karmic seeds that lead to later outcomes.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Punishments are results of karmic effects.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Rewards are results of karmic effects.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In Buddhism, the bodhisattva that is believed to become the next buddha is called Maitreya. He lives in Tusita Heaven, where he will wait until his rebirth in the human realm to become the next Buddha. This will occur once the Dharma and all the current Buddha's relics are forgotten and destroyed. Maitreya's name and character appears several times in the text.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: In Buddhism, the bodhisattva that is believed to become the next buddha is called Maitreya. He lives in Tusita Heaven, where he will wait until his rebirth in the human realm to become the next Buddha. This will occur once the Dharma and all the current Buddha's relics are forgotten and destroyed. Maitreya's name and character appears several times in the text.

↳ Alive, identified

– Yes

Notes: Maiteya lives in Tusita Heaven.

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– No

Notes: Maitreya will become a Buddha once the Dharma and all the current Buddha's relics are forgotten and destroyed.

↳ Coming on a specified date

– No

Notes: Maitreya will become a Buddha once the Dharma and all the current Buddha's relics are forgotten and destroyed.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– No

Notes: Maitreya will become a Buddha once the Dharma and all the current Buddha's relics are forgotten and destroyed.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

Notes: Maitreya will become a Buddha once the Dharma and all the current Buddha's relics are forgotten and destroyed.

↳ Coming has already passed

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– Yes

Notes: Maitreya will become a Buddha once the Dharma and all the current Buddha's relics are forgotten and destroyed. There were many before him, and there will be more after him.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

Notes: In Buddhism, the bodhisattva that is believed to become the next buddha is called Maitreya. He lives in Tusita Heaven, where he will wait until his rebirth in the human realm to become the next Buddha. He will restore the teaching of the Dharma.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

Notes: In Buddhism, the bodhisattva that is believed to become the next buddha is called Maitreya. He lives in Tusita Heaven, where he will wait until his rebirth in the human realm to become the next Buddha. He will restore the teaching of the Dharma.

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: Promulgate the Dharma

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are minor references to the final destruction of the world in the text. This refers to the general South Asian cosmological belief that the world is created, existent, and destroyed in cycles that extend over thousands of thousands of years. The text notes that this will occur thousands of thousands of years from now.

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↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

Notes: There are minor references to the final destruction of the world in the text. This refers to the general South Asian cosmological belief that the world is created, existent, and destroyed in cycles that extend over thousands of thousands of years. The text notes that this will occur thousands of thousands of years from now.

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
– No

↳ Divine judgment event
– No

↳ Restoration of the world
– Yes

Notes: There are minor references to the final destruction of the world in the text. This refers to the general South Asian cosmological belief that the world is created, existent, and destroyed in cycles that extend over thousands of thousands of years. The text notes that this will occur thousands of thousands of years from now.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
– Yes

Notes: There are minor references to the final destruction of the world in the text. This refers to the general South Asian cosmological belief that the world is created, existent, and destroyed in cycles that extend over thousands of thousands of years. The text notes that this will occur thousands of thousands of years from now.

↳ Establishment of new political system
– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system
– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?
– Specify: This refers to the general South Asian cosmological belief that the world is created, existent, and destroyed in cycles that extend over thousands of thousands of years. The text notes that this will occur thousands of thousands of years from now.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
– I don't know
Notes: There are minor references to the final destruction of the world in the text. This refers to the general South Asian cosmological belief that the world is created, existent, and destroyed in cycles that extend over thousands of thousands of years. The text notes that this will occur thousands of thousands of years from now.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: This text itself does not prescribe any social norms, but it does refer to a wide variety of moral codes within the Buddhist canons which do.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions the two (conventional and ultimate) truths of Mahayana Buddhism in a few different places. The conventional truth is that the wind exists, and the ultimate truth is that the wind is empty. These are different but parallels ideas, so they are not oppositional.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

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↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

Notes: The text mentions the two (conventional and ultimate) truths of Mahayana Buddhism in a few different places. The conventional truth is that the wind exists, and the ultimate truth is that the wind is empty. These are different but parallels ideas, so they are not oppositional.

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https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: This text itself does not prescribe any moral norms, but it does refer to a wide variety of moral codes within the Buddhist canons which do.

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The figures in this text are highlighted for their various virtues. Few all have the same virtues, but I will highlight those which are lauded.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– No
- ↳ Cooperation
– No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No

- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues
 - Yes
 - Notes: Elegance

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not require this practice, but it does present Buddhist figures who engage in this practice.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– No

↳ Food taboos?

– Yes

Notes: Quite a few Buddhist figures in the text engage in vegetarianism, but it is not universal among all figures present in the text.

↳ Hair?

– Yes

Notes: A number of Buddhist figures in the text receive tonsure (shaving the scalp) upon becoming monastics, but not all figures in the text undergo this practice.

↳ Dress?

– Yes

Notes: Monastic figures in the text are described to have worn specific robes. Not all figures in this text performed this practice, however.

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: There are several instances of Buddhist figures reading and translating Sanskrit texts in this text.

↳ Other?

– Specify: No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not use these terms, but it is quite common for Buddhist texts to use fictive kinship terminology when referring to the Buddhist Sangha.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: Shi HuiJiao makes a point in his postface that he included all aspects of virtue and removed all undeserved compliments and repetition. It was intended as a compilation of a vast number of eminent figures to highlight those with virtue in order to preserve their stories rather than for entertainment, which HuiJiao notes occurs in other compilations.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82%t

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not specify rules or forms of practice which should be followed. Instead, it presents Buddhist figures performing a wide variety of practices.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A chiefdom

Notes: This is the closest thing to a Buddhist Temple structure among this group. A head monastic/teacher with a sort of hierarchical strata of monastics and students.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: This text was produced within the Liang Dynasty, and its reproduction was supported by later dynasties.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: There are several instances of Buddhist persecution in its history in China. These usually resulted in the destruction of texts.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: Although it does not codify it. There are several stories in the text discussing the responses of Buddhist figures to famine, such as the story of Shi Fajin of Gaochang.

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https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82%t

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: Although it does not codify it. There are several stories in the text discussing the responses of Buddhist figures to poverty, such as the story of Shi Zhiyan of Zhiyuan Temple.

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Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: Although it does not codify it. There are several stories in the text discussing the responses of Buddhist figures to the elderly and sick, such as the story of Shi Senglue of Da Temple in Chang'an.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82%t

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: There are a wide variety of reactions of Buddhist figures mentioned in the text, but there are no clear codifications of welfare methods within this specific text.

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Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are historically Buddhist institutions that taught Buddhist texts, but it is unclear if this text was taught specifically.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are many references to student-teacher relationships between the figures mentioned in the text and their teachers/students. These appear in a variety of contexts.

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Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: The text does mention non-Buddhist education in relation to a variety of figures, but it does not codify it.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– Yes

Notes: The text does not codify these ratios, but there are quite a few instances of direct master-student relationships and larger teacher-students lectures.

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Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Education and training would potentially lead to spiritual attainments and worldly renown.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

Notes: Not specifically, but there are instances of Buddhist figures advocating for food distribution from imperial coffers to the public during disasters.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022. [https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E)

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not codify this, but there are instances of Buddhist figures advocating for food distribution from imperial coffers to the public during disasters. See the story of Shi Fajin of Gaochang.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022. [https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E)

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– No

Notes: The text mentions civic functions occurring, but it does not codify any aspects of them.

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↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– No

Notes: The text mentions justice practice occurring, but it does not codify any aspects of them.

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↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

Notes: The text mentions floods and related disasters, but it does not codify any responses.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022. [https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E!](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E)

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: There are quite a few interactions with a variety of public works in the text, but non are specifically codified by the text itself.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Notes: Taxes from families and regions are indicated as gifts to Buddhist figures, but the details are not discussed beyond this.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.

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Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions a variety of civil wars between dynasties prior to the Liang Dynasty. There are some details about imperial power struggles that involved some Buddhist figures. See the stories of Kumārajīva of Chang'an and Zhu Fo Tucheng of Zhong Temple in Yecheng.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions a few instances of Buddhist figures leading to the liberation of prisoners. See the story of Shi Sengbao of Qihuan Temple in the Capital.

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Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions a variety of types of food production and disbursement throughout the stories. There are no specific codifications about their uses.

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↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Notes: The text mentions how Buddhist practitioners would farm and do food production related work, but it does not dictate any regulation. See the story of Shi Dao'an of Wuji Temple.

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Yes

Notes: The text quite often mentions lay practitioners offering food to the Buddhist figures as a

form of respect, but it does also critique over offering. See the story of Buddhahadra of Daochang Temple in Chang'an.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82%B3

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]

– Cannibalism

Notes: There is an instance of ordained cannibalism in the story of Shi Fajin of Gaochang. He offers his thigh meat, dipped in salt, to the poor during a famine. This is considered a form of self immolation.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'A7%E5%82%B3](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83%A7%E5%82%B3)

– Fishing

Notes: Fishing is mentioned in passing, but it is not associated with temple work. See the story of Beidu.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'A7%E5%82%B3)

– Pastoralism

Notes: Herding is mentioned in passing as a form of servitude, but it is not associated with temple work. See the story of Shi Huirui of Wuyi Temple in the Capital.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'A7%E5%82%B3)

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Notes: Hunting is generally presented as an action which accrues negative karma. Some Buddhist figures avoid it, while others do not. See the story of Cuṇavarman of Qihuan Temple in the Capital and Zhu Shulan.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
[https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'](https://www.academia.edu/90233933/Shi_HuiJiao_The_Biographies_of_Eminent_Monks_%E9%AB%98%E5%83'A7%E5%82%B3)

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Several Buddhist figures in the text engage in farming as part of their monastic training.

Reference: Shi HuiJiao. *Biographies of Eminent Monks*. Edited by Edward A S Ross. Translated by Tianshu Yang. Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, University of Hong Kong, 2022.
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↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

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Entry/Answer References

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